

cards *of clarity*

IN DIALOGUE

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GETTING STARTED

These cards are designed to support moderators in navigating moments of challenge, ambiguity, or tension during deliberative discussions.

They offer clear signals to notice, interpretations to consider, and practical tools to respond constructively.

Grounded in research on dialogue and argumentation, these cards translate theory into usable guidance for real-time facilitation in ORBIS and similar democratic platforms.

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DESIGNED FOR DELIBERATION

This deck draws from guidelines developed for conflict prevention, management, and resolution within the ORBIS deliberative democracy platforms.

The cards aim to:

- Improve inclusive participation
- Anticipate or respond to emerging tension
- Support respectful, productive argumentation
- They align with ORBIS goals of fostering better democratic discourse.

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THE ORIGIN

The content is based on qualitative research into real dispute mediation interactions and deliberative events from ORBIS use cases.

Researchers analyzed:

- Over 180,000 words of mediated dialogue
- Transcripts and recordings from ORBIS pilots
- Patterns of silence, emotional tension, conflict framing, and more
- Findings were coded using both inductive and deductive approaches.

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FROM INSIGHTS TO ACTION

The cards connect emerging needs to practical tools, drawn from both research and observed discussions.

Each card links:

- A recognizable challenge
- A set of discursive cues
- A reflective interpretation
- A set of concrete moderator actions
- This method helps transfer complex research into simple, actionable formats.

QUIET
CORNERS

LACK OF PARTICIPATION FROM CERTAIN
INDIVIDUALS OR GROUPS.

QUIET CORNERS

INDICATORS

Same speakers dominate; long silences; visible disengagement.

INSIGHT

Possible “cold conflict” or disengagement due to exclusion. Decisions risk to be taken without real agreement by participants.

RESPONSE

“I’d like to invite someone we haven’t heard from yet.”

OPTIONAL MOVE

Allow participants to share thoughts privately or at a different time.

DOMINATING VOICE

ONE OR MORE INDIVIDUALS MONOPOLIZE
THE DISCUSSION.

DOMINATING VOICES

INDICATORS

Frequent interruptions;
imbalance in talk time.

INSIGHT

Risk of marginalizing minority perspectives.

RESPONSE

“Let’s make space to hear from
different perspectives.”

OPTIONAL MOVE

Time-limited rounds or speaking tokens.

FRAGMENTED FOCUS

SCATTERED DISCUSSION
LACKING COHERENCE.

FRAGMENTED FOCUS

INDICATORS

Many discussion issues raised without cohesion or closure.

INSIGHT

Scattered input on different issues prevents focus and progress.

RESPONSE

Refocus the group on one core issue and see if there are important sub-issues that need to be addressed.

OPTIONAL MOVE

Create a visual issue tree or shared notes board.

CIRCLING THE ISSUES

PARTICIPANTS CIRCLE THE PROBLEM
WITHOUT MOVING TO SOLUTIONS.

CIRCLING THE ISSUES

INDICATORS

Ideas repeat with no forward motion or resolution.

INSIGHT

Endless cycles reduce effectiveness and energy and participants lose faith in discussions.

RESPONSE

Pause to summarize and propose moving to solutions.

OPTIONAL MOVE

Split into breakout groups to develop proposals.

BENEATH THE SURFACE

PARTICIPANTS EXPRESS FIXED POSITIONS,
BUT NOT UNDERLYING CONCERNS.

BENEATH THE SURFACE

INDICATORS

Positions stated without explanations of underlying concerns.

INSIGHT

Interests behind positions remain hidden.

RESPONSE

Ask 'What's important to you about this position?'

OPTIONAL MOVE

What is important for us and for others?
Offer and ask about concerns and reasons underlying positions.

MEETING THE OTHER

DISMISSIVE OR ADVERSARIAL TONE
TOWARD OTHER VIEWPOINTS.

MEETING THE OTHER

INDICATORS

Dismissive language or lack of acknowledgment.

INSIGHT

Without recognizing others, respect erodes in the discussion.

RESPONSE

Prompt 'Could you reformulate what you heard from them?'

OPTIONAL MOVE

Invite storytelling or ask for lived experience. Or invite to ask others' lived experience and listen to them.

SHIFTING THE LENS

LACK OF SHARED UNDERSTANDING OR
BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE.

SHIFTING THE LENS

INDICATORS

Confusion due to differing levels of knowledge or different perspectives.

INSIGHT

Participants lack shared foundations to engage.

RESPONSE

Clarify key terms and acknowledge differing perspectives where needed.

OPTIONAL MOVE

Provide brief background or context, and invite participants to agree to disagree when alignment isn't possible.

THE FIRE BENEATH

EMOTIONAL UNDERCURRENTS SUCH
AS ANGER OR FEAR.

THE FIRE BENEATH

INDICATORS

Tense tone, emotional outbursts, long silences. Look out for language that expresses emotions, like “I’m disappointed,” “I’m angry,” “I’m worried.” etc.

INSIGHT

Emotions often mask deeper concerns.

RESPONSE

Use 'I hear this matters to you— can you tell us more?'

OPTIONAL MOVE

Acknowledge emotions and sentiments as legitimate and ask if people want to share more.

FROM SELF
TO SYSTEM

PARTICIPANTS PERSONALIZE
BLAME OR GUILT.

FROM SELF TO SYSTEM

INDICATORS

Blame, guilt, or personalization of issues.

INSIGHT

Personalization blocks collaborative dialogue.

RESPONSE

Reframe: 'Many others also face this challenge.'
Or 'it is normal in this kind of discussion to
have disagreement'

OPTIONAL MOVE

Disagreement is not a failure! Acknowledge
that disagreement is normal in dialogue and
remove guilt.

EMPTY
CHAIR

KEY VOICES MISSING FROM
THE CONVERSATION.

EMPTY CHAIR

INDICATORS

Statements like 'we can't move forward without them.'

INSIGHT

Missing stakeholders weaken discussion legitimacy.

RESPONSE

Ask 'Who else needs to be here for this to work?'

OPTIONAL MOVE

Create an outreach plan or schedule follow-up if important voices are missing.

GUIDELINES FOR USE

1. Start with the Intro Cards to understand the structure, purpose, and categories.
2. Use cards in real time, as preparation, or for post-session reflection.
3. Participant View cards are designed as light-touch signals, visible only to moderators, to help respond to emerging group needs.
4. Cards are not prescriptive, but reflective tools to support dialogic awareness and inclusion.

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All sources can be accessed open access at:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/orbis-heu>

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ORBIS

ORBIS is a European Union-funded project that develops digital platforms to support deliberative democracy.

It aims to enhance inclusive participation, conflict prevention, and collaborative decision-making through tools based on dialogue and argumentation research.

To know more, visit : orbis-project.eu

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ACCESS GUIDELINES

You can access guidelines
complementing cards at:
zenodo.org/communities/orbis-heu
or you can scan the QR code below.

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